

Report on communication, dissemination and exploitation activities

Front page of *Nature*, 24th September 2020. Ricarda Winkelmann, Julius Garbe and their co-authors publish a paper on the hysteresis of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. The study shows that as Earth's climate becomes warmer, the ice sheet becomes progressively more sensitive to a given amount of warming. If warming levels persist, to restore the ice sheet to its current form would require a cooling to lower than pre-industrial levels. The paper belongs to the Top25 climate papers most featured in the media in 2020.

TiPACCs: Tipping points in Antarctic Climate Component is a Research and Innovation action (RIA) funded by the Horizon 2020 Work programme topics addressed: LC-CLA-08-2018 Addressing knowledge gaps in climate science, in support of IPCC reports. Start date: 1 August 2019. End date: 31 July 2023

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About this document

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Summary for publication

The TiPACCs project aims at determining the likelihood of large and abrupt near-future changes in the contribution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet to global sea level, caused by tipping points in the Antarctic continental shelf seas and the Antarctic Ice Sheet. The topic has sparked great interest within the scientific community, among stakeholders and the general public. The consortium therefore agreed on a dedicated Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan to coordinate all CDE activities, which is updated on a regular basis. The entire TiPACCs consortium actively engages in the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts of the results in various ways.

Main outcomes so far include the launch of the TiPACCs website, regular newsletters and press releases (e.g., 'North scientists researching the dangers of melting Antarctic ice sheets', '£4m study to investigate if climate change will drive the Antarctic Ice Sheet towards a tipping point', 'Stability Check on Antarctica Reveals High Risk for Long-Term Sea-Level Rise'), the establishment of a social media strategy (including the @TiPACCs_EU twitter account) and numerous scientific and public talks from all project partners including early-career scientist. Several conferences were hosted and organized by TiPACCs members, e.g., the Elmer/Ice beginner course, EGU 2020 sessions ITS3.1/NP1.2 on 'Tipping Points in the Earth System' and CR5.4 on 'Ice-sheet and climate interactions', as well as the Forum for Research into Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP 2020).

Notably, the first video of the TiPACCs video series, explaining the tipping points in ice and ocean to a broad audience, was published in February 2020. To this point, the video on the TiPACCs-own YouTube channel has created more than 1300 views, and many more through the usage in lectures and presentations which cannot be counted. The scripting process for the second video focusing on the ocean tipping points is already underway.

The consortium has further engaged in providing expert guidance to policy makers. Several project members have served as reviewers for the upcoming 6th Assessment Report of the IPCC, and Ricarda Winkelmann is actively involved in writing the Earth Commission Report (expected publication in 2022).

In the upcoming months, we will continue our efforts on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation based on new scientific insights from Work Packages 1, 2 and 3. By linking the modelling results with available and ongoing Southern Ocean observations, our work will create the basis for a scientific report for an early-warning system regarding global sea-level rise.

Links built

All members within the TiPACCs consortium are actively engaged in the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts. This deliverable therefore links to all WPs. As an example, over the past months, several meetings to script and design the upcoming videos for the TiPACCs video series took place, creating a direct link between the ongoing research and CDE activities. Externally, links have been built with for example the coordination of H2020 project PROTECT coordinated by University of Grenoble. For more information on collaborations with other projects and initiatives, see Deliverable 5.10.

Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Lead authors

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(I) Summary

The Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation (CDE) Plan was designed and produced by the Coordinators and Leads of WP4 and WP5 based on the feedback and assistance given by the EU Commissioner during the TiPACCs Kick-Off meeting (October 2-4, 2019) in Bergen, Norway.

The basis for the strategy was the schematic Figure 9 produced earlier in the Description of Action (DoA). Using target audiences, objectives and communications tools identified in this document as a starting point, we extrapolated on the information to produce a more comprehensive and detailed strategy. We cluster these activities along the three main objectives: communication, dissemination and exploitation, reproduced from EU guidelines (see Fig. 1).

	COMMUNICATION	DISSEMINATION	EXPLOITATION
OBJECTIVE	Reach out to society and show the impacts and benefits of EU-funded R&I activities	Transfer knowledge & results with the aim to enable others to use and take up results	Effectively use project results through scientific, economic, political or societal exploitation routes → aim to make a concrete value and impact for society
FOCUS	Inform about and promote the project AND its results/success.	Describe and ensure results available for others to USE → focus on results only	Make concrete use of results (for scientific, societal or economic purposes)
TARGET AUDIENCE	Multiple audiences beyond the project's own community (incl. media and public)	Audiences that may take an interest in the potential USE of the results (e.g. scientific community, industrial partner, policy makers, etc.)	Project partners (individuals or organisations) and groups outside the project that make concrete use of the results

Figure 1: Overview of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities. Reproduced from EU guidelines.

All CDE activities will be coordinated and managed by CDE manager Jørund Raukleiv Strømsøe, in collaboration with WP4 lead Ricarda Winkelmann.

(II) Objectives

TiPACCs is designed to **determine the likelihood of large and abrupt near-future changes in the contribution of the Antarctic Ice Sheet to global sea level, caused by tipping points in the Antarctic continental shelf seas and the Antarctic Ice Sheet.** The project, hence, will, deliver information that will flow directly into the next IPCC Assessment Report (e.g., the chapter on Ocean, Cryosphere and Sea Level) as well as the Earth Commission Report (expected publication in 2022) and provide expert guidance to policy makers. In addition, our modelling work will provide parameter estimates of safe operating spaces, allowing the tipping points in ice and ocean to be quantified. By linking these with available and ongoing Southern Ocean observations, our results will create the basis for a scientific report for an early-warning system regarding global sea-level rise.

It is therefore vital that the entire TiPACCs consortium engages in the communication, dissemination and exploitation efforts of our results.

During the TiPACCs Kick-Off meeting in Bergen (in October 2019), we held a session on CDE activities, in order to clearly communicate the benefits of an effective CDE strategy for the whole consortium and each individual partner, and also discussed the risks in case a clear action plan was not followed. We clarified the aims and target groups for each task to the new consortium members and identified a **core group of representatives responsible for reporting and streamlining the CDE activities**, with one representative from each partner institution:

AWI: Klaus Grosfeld

NORCE: Jørund R. Strømsøe

PIK: Ricarda Winkelmann

UGA: Olivier Gagliardini

UNN: Christopher Bull

We have further created an **online tool** which will help us collect information on talks, panel discussions, school projects and other CDE activities related to our work within TiPACCs by individual researchers in the consortium. A reminder is sent out to the CDE representatives every two weeks to ensure a regular and timely update on these activities.

To make the results of the TiPACCs project available as widely as possible and to effectively reach out to our target audiences, a dedicated, revised CDE plan, engaging the entire consortium, is described below. The CDE strategy will consist of three consecutive phases (see Fig. 2).

Figure 2: Three phases on TiPACCs CDE strategy. The awareness-oriented phase (M1-M12) is followed by the result-oriented phase (M12-M48) and exploitation-oriented phase (M12-M48).

(III) Target Audiences

Target audiences had already been defined in WP4 as well as the impacts section (see Figure 9) of the proposal. However, during the writing of the strategy, it was deemed appropriate to specify and consolidate the planned activities with particular target audiences in mind.

Broad target audience	Target audience	Brief description
Scientific community	Specialist scientific community	The specialist scientific community is made up of scientists working across the disciplines directly addressed in the work of TiPACCs, focusing on, e.g., climate science, climate modelling, oceanography and glaciology.
	European and international initiatives and projects	Other European and international initiatives, major scientific organisations (SCAR, FRISP) and projects include, e.g., Model Intercomparison Projects (MIPs), linked (EU and other) projects and the EU Polar Cluster
End user groups	School educators and higher education course leaders delivering climate science	This stakeholder group are those based in school and higher education institutions, engaged in disseminating high-level knowledge and information to students and professionals studying in the field. These organizations will have a keen interest in acquiring the most up-to date information.
	Policy makers and the EU Commission	Policy makers and EU Commission services are the decision makers who have the power and responsibility to set policy based on information they receive. New knowledge and information developed as a result of TiPACCs will be relevant to decision makers at all levels of governance from local to EU and global levels.
	Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)	Non-governmental organizations are those who operate in the sphere of civil society. They are often interest groups who work and campaign for certain issues. Those relevant to TiPACCs are likely to be involved in environmental protection and coastal protection although those working in other fields may also be relevant.
General public	Wider scientifically interested community	The wider, scientifically interested community is made up of scientists who do not directly work across the disciplines addressed by TiPACCs but still may harbor an interest in the results of the project.
	General public and wider society	The general public and wider society represent individuals and organizations who are interested in the work and results of TiPACCs as a matter of interest. This group may include private citizens, students and others who are not direct targets of the TiPACCs communications strategy.

Note that in many cases, specific tasks relate to more than one target audience. Likewise, some of the tasks might serve communication, dissemination and exploitation aims at the same time. The following should therefore be understood as an overview of the planned CDE activities, identifying a main target audience and dominant purpose.

(IV) Communication Activities

Overview of activities

Activity	Task in DoA	Target audience
C.1 Project website	Task 4.1	General public and society
C.2 Newsletters and press releases	Task 4.1	General public and society, wider scientifically interested community
C.3 Social media strategy @TiPACCs_EU	Task 4.1	General public and society, Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)
C.4 Interactive maps	Task 4.6	School educators and higher education course leaders delivering climate science
C.5 Video series	Task 4.5	General public and society, School educators and higher education course leaders delivering climate science
C.6 Communications training for TiPACCs members	Task 4.4	TiPACCs consortium
C.7 High-school teacher training	Task 4.4	School educators
C.8 Further communication activities	Task 4.1	General public and society, Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

Communication tasks

Task C.1: Project website (M1-48)

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: General public and society

Shortly after the start of the project, a **project website (D4.1)** was established which is regularly updated and serves as a **main hub to link our CDE activities**. In order to exchange project documentation and model results between the partners, we have also set up a restricted area which only the project partners have access to. On the public area of the website, CDE materials such as model results and press releases will continue to be posted.

Task C.2: Newsletters and press releases (M1-48)

Task lead: NORCE, PIK

Target audience: General public and society, wider scientifically interested community

In order to maximize the impact and exploitation of our research results, we will regularly put out press releases (for instance when new papers are published). A first press release was published in October 2019 to announce the start of the TiPACCs project (<https://www.alphagalileo.org/en-gb/Item-Display/ItemId/184500?returnurl=https://www.alphagalileo.org/en-gb/Item-Display/ItemId/184500>).

All partner institutes also have very active PR departments, publishing regular newsletters and press releases which frequently get covered by media outlets worldwide. To give some examples, AWI publishes a monthly newsletter with 1200 recipients, and their most recent press releases which were sent out to several hundred journalists each resulted in 70-1000 articles in German newspapers, reaching 4 to 30 million readers. The Bjerknes Center for Climate Research publishes a newsletter with about 2000 recipients and also frequent articles in the “tograder” magazine (<https://energiogklima.no/tograder/>). A recently funded project (PROPHET) at UNN made it on the first-page of the largest local newspaper in the Northeast of England with an additional two-page coverage within the newspaper (readership is on the order of 100 000).

Where related to TiPACCs activities, we will link these newsletters and press releases on the TiPACCs webpage.

Task C.3: Social media strategy @TiPACCs_EU (M1-48)

Task lead: NORCE, PIK

Target audience: General public and society, Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

We will further engage in **social media** activities, led and structured by an appointed social media representative. To this aim, we have established the handle @TiPACCs_EU as well as the hashtag #AntarcticTipping in order to keep track of related threads in the online community. Currently, the media representatives at each institution have access to the twitter account, but all consortium members are encouraged to link to it and post using the respective hashtags.

Rather than dispersing information via many different channels, we have decided to focus on twitter and facebook as our main social media outlet, not least because this will allow us to exploit already established social media channels from consortium members to instantly reach a **wider whilst targeted audience**.

Twitter: With a total of currently **more than 100,000 followers** (@AWI-medien with 6,000, @AWI-media with 3,800, @NorthumbriaUni with 33,600, @PIK_Klima with 12,700, @PIK_Climate with 11,300, @BjerknesBCCR with 4,100 followers, @NORCEresearch with 980, @UGrenobleAlpes with 7,600, @OSUG_fr with 1,300, @IGE_Grenoble with 485, @BAS_News with 34,500 followers), twitter is already an important part of the partner’s social media communication.

In addition to the institutes’ twitter accounts, several members of the consortium are also personally very active on twitter - Anders Levermann (@ALevermann) for instance has 3800 followers/3100 likes, and there is a twitter channel by the Elmer/Ice group (@ElmerIce1, 180 followers). We plan to build on this existent twitter network to communicate with a wider audience, distribute news and results from the project, all efforts consolidated using our joint @TiPACCs_EU handle.

Facebook: Next to twitter, the partners' Facebook pages with **more than 125,000 followers** also provide a large existent network of scientists, stakeholders and the interested public, which we will utilize as multiplier for news on model results and publications as well as press releases.

- UNN: @NorthumbriaUniversity with 82,000 followers
- AWI: German - @AlfredWegenerInstitut with 13,500 followers; English - @AlfredWegenerInstitute with 3,500 followers
- PIK: @PIKPotsdam with around 1,500 followers
- NORCE: @Bjerknessenteret with 2,000 followers; @norceresearch with 2,000 followers
- UGA: French - @UGGrenobleAlpes with 18,000 followers; International - @UGAInternational with 5,500 followers

Task C.4: Interactive maps (M25-45)

Task lead: UGA

Target audience: School educators and higher education course leaders delivering climate science

During the course of the project, UGA will develop a **web-based interface** to present the main results of the project. It will consist in designing **interactive maps (D4.10)** which will feature:

- Basic information on the Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean
- Information on the different ice shelves and drainage basins (e.g., grounding line position, ice thickness, ice velocities, temperature, bottom topography) and Antarctic marginal seas (e.g., bottom topography, temperature, salinity, and ocean currents)
- Sub-ice shelf drilling sites and ship-born data
- TiPACCs model results, e.g., critical ocean temperatures and salinities (and the respective uncertainties) at which grounding lines for the different drainage basins might become unstable.

By allowing the users to modify the model forcing, the interactive maps will demonstrate the existence of the tipping points that might arise in Antarctica. The maps will be designed using open source tools (e.g. visualizer <https://github.com/kitware/visualizer> and ParaviewWeb <https://kitware.github.io/paraviewweb/>). They will be directly based on the model results produced during the course of the project. The design and conception of the web interface will be done by 2 x 6-month master training of a computer scientist engineer student. The deployment of the web interface will be done on a dedicated local server.

The interactive maps will be a lasting synthesis of our results, and as such can be used for educational purposes in **high-school and university projects** and in **public talks**, also well beyond the end of the project period.

Task C.5: Video series on Tipping Points in Antarctic Climate Components (M1-6; M22-27; M34-39; M43-45)

Task lead: UNN, PIK

Target audience: General public and society, School educators and higher education course leaders delivering climate science

In addition to providing our scientific results to policy and decision makers, it is of great importance to also make our findings available to the broader public. To this aim, we will create a **video series (D4.6-D4.9)** which will be published on a **specially established YouTube channel** or other video-sharing websites.

We choose the video format to reach as wide an audience as possible and pursue several objectives simultaneously, namely to:

- Introduce some of the fundamentals of ocean and ice dynamics in Antarctica to the broader public
- Provide first insights into our research methods
- Make the results of our latest TiPACCs research intelligible to all levels of education.

Beyond providing fundamental scientific information, we aim to put our findings into the broader context of the climate change debate and to “give climate science a face”. Ultimately, we hope to communicate not only the relevance of these research topics but also our fascination with the Antarctic Ice Sheet and the Southern Ocean.

Each WP is planned to feature in at least one short video of 5-15 minutes length. The first video will be an introduction to the TiPACCs project, partners and funding agency. The other videos will cover fundamental facts on the Antarctic Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean, and basic concepts such as tipping points or grounding line stability. The content and material will be provided by the TiPACCs consortium, using external support for the filming, editing and production of the videos. The format will be chosen depending on the topic, ranging from short interviews to animations of modelling results.

To make the videos most accessible we will promote them via our own social media channels (see Task 4.3) including partner YouTube channels (@AWIResearch, @PotsdamInstitute, @CommunautéUniversitéGrenobleAlpes). We also intend to reach out to well-established science channels to promote them further (contacts exist for instance to National Geographic) and provide them to collaborating school classes.

Task C.6: Communications training for TiPACCs members (M12, M24)

Task lead: UNN

Target audience: TiPACCs consortium

Partnering with **NUSTEM** (Northumbria University, Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics) we are planning dedicated communication training for the TiPACCs members. All researchers will receive training and support in science communication to allow them to share the research and its importance with a range of public audiences.

Aims:

- Improve science communication skills amongst consortium partners suitable for working with children, young people and adults.
- Share best practice within and between the consortium partners
- Develop adaptable outreach resources for use with different audiences
- Support effective evaluation of outreach activities.

The science communication training will provide an introduction to public engagement for junior and senior researchers involved in the consortium. These will take the form of two distinct half-day workshops and include information about motivations for public engagement, planning for evaluation and impact, communicating with different audiences and linking research to school curricula. Participants will also be provided with three exemplar workshop/activities which can be adapted for different audiences (for children between 7 and 11, young people between 12 and 14, families), and editable evaluation tools. The workshops will take place in conjunction with the annual meeting of the project in year 2 (M12, **D4.3**) and year 3 (M24, **D4.4**).

Task C.7: Teacher Training (M34)

Task lead: UNN

Target audience: School educators

To enable scaling of outreach activities for our pan-European project, Northumbria University, through **NUSTEM** (Northumbria University, Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics), an outreach and research group based at UNN, will develop and deliver teacher training on issues related to Antarctic tipping points (**D4.5**). Teachers will attend a workshop which will explain the science behind the research and provide activity ideas to introduce the research in their schools. NUSTEM works closely with over 40 partner schools, both primary and secondary, to provide regular and sustained contact with children, young people and their key influencers: teachers and families. Since its formation in 2014, NUSTEM has had over 85000 interactions with children, teachers, parents and other adults, with many of these interactions being 'repeat visits' to provide ongoing support to participants.

Aims:

- Increase awareness of Antarctic research with a particular focus on the use of models to determine tipping points in climate change.
- Increase confidence in using cutting edge research in the classroom
- Provide worksheets and activity ideas that can be used in the school situation.

A training session for teachers will be developed and delivered at two practitioner conferences. One possible forum would be the EGU General Assembly (M34), and a second forum would be the Annual conference of the Association for Science Education. Both conferences attract an international audience. The materials developed would be made available online through NUSTEM at Northumbria University as well project partner websites.

Task C.8: Further communication activities (M1-M48)

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: General public and society, Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

All consortium members are already actively involved in numerous communication and public outreach activities established via individual or institutional channels. These are not necessarily part of a TiPACCs deliverable, but since some of these are highly relevant within the scope of TiPACCs, we will consolidate and further maximize the reach of these activities using our project website and twitter account. These further communication activities are gathered through an online tool specifically set up for this purpose. A reminder is sent out by NORCE to the CDE representatives every two weeks to ensure a regular and timely update on these activities.

Such activities range **from public talks to, science slams, high-school activities, and science-meets-arts events**. To name a few recent examples, AWI organizes bi-annual Open House Days as well as guided tours at the institute, and like PIK, the institute participates in the yearly Girls Day, an initiative to foster particularly young girls' interest in natural sciences and mathematics. AWI is further involved in 'Science on the Road' (<https://www.awi.de/imfokus/wissenschaftsjahr/science-on-the-road.html>). NORCE engages in the annual Bjerknes Day (several events targeting school children and the general public) and Science Days (with a large open science fair). PIK is involved in the annual Long Night of Science and Potsdam Science Day. As an active member of the German Young Academy, Ricarda Winkelmann further engages in a number of public outreach activities, school academies, and science-meets-arts events (such as the annual Salon Sophie Charlotte or expert discussion, e.g. during the Potsdam film premiere 'Zwischen Himmel und Eis' by Oscar award winner Luc Jacquet). She also contributed to the MOOC "Climate Change – a question of justice?" by Fern-Universität Hagen and Lund University". BAS participates in the annual Cambridge Science Festival, and UNN organizes annual 'open door' events for the general public where staff members present latest research. As a part of a funded NERC project, Hilmar Gudmundsson is also collaborating with the children books

author Darragh Martin on a book about Antarctica aimed at children. UGA is involved every year in the national science day (“journées de la science”) by presenting didactic experiments of glaciers and ice-sheets. The IGE at UGA organises regular guided tour of the institute for schools. UGA participants are regularly invited to broader public conferences to speak about Cryosphere and climate change.

Science Blogs: Several members of the consortium regularly post on science blogs, including the well-established climate blog RealClimate (<http://www.realclimate.org/>) as well as the German climate science blog Klimalounge (<https://scilogs.spektrum.de/klimalounge>), where Anders Levermann is one of the main authors. AWI has several active blogs, including the AWI Ice Blog and expedition blogs (see <https://blogs.helmholtz.de/en>). On the recent expedition PS111 to the southern Weddell Sea with research vessel Polarstern operated by AWI, Ricarda Winkelmann also wrote a blog series for the German Newspaper ‘Frankfurter Allgemeine Zeitung’ (<http://blogs.faz.net/antarktis/>) where the posts achieved overall more than 40,000 reads. UNN staff members frequently contribute to ‘The Conversation’ (<http://theconversation.com/uk>).

(V) Dissemination Activities

Overview of activities

Activity	Task in DoA	Target audience
D.1 Publications and special issue	Task 4.2	Specialist scientific community
D.2 Scientific conferences and workshops	Task 4.2	Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects
D.3 IPCC and Earth Commission	Task 4.7	Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)
D.4 Stakeholder event	Task 4.7	Local government in the area of Bremen, German media and national decision makers
D.5 Report for policy makers	Task 4.8	Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

Dissemination tasks

Task D.1: Publications and special issue (M1-48)

Task lead: PIK, UNN

Target audience: Specialist scientific community

We will disseminate our results to scientific communities by publishing ('gold' standard) **open-access peer-reviewed articles** (e.g., in *The Cryosphere*, *Journal of Glaciology*, *Geoscience Model Development*, *Journal of Physical Oceanography*, *Geophysical Research Letters*, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, *Journal of Climate*).

We are further planning a **special issue on Tipping Points in the Earth System**, most likely under the umbrella of ISI-journal *The Cryosphere*. This would make TiPACCs the lead in a much larger endeavor, to understand the dynamics and interaction of tipping elements in the Earth System, including our own results on Antarctic tipping points, but also further results on other tipping elements such as the Amazon rainforest, monsoon systems or the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation. The special issue will be open for submission for the next 5 years, which will also ensure the availability and continuation of our results well beyond the end of the TiPACCs project.

Task D.2: Scientific conferences and workshops (M1-48)

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

We will continue to actively participate in conferences and workshops. This includes the presentation of our results at smaller expert workshops and the major international conferences such as EGU, AGU and IGS annual meetings at which we also intend to submit sessions dedicated to the topic of Antarctic tipping points. We will specifically target the two coming IGS symposia on topics which are very relevant regarding

TiPACCs, namely the International Symposium on Ice Stream Dynamics (2020 in Durham, UK) and the International Symposium on Interactions of Ice Sheets and Glaciers with the Ocean (2021 in La Jolla, California, USA). Moreover, during the project period, the Forum for Research into Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP) conference will be hosted in the UK (2019) and PIK (2020).

Task D.3: IPCC and Earth Commission (M1-48)

Task lead: PIK

Target audience: Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

Several members of the TiPACCs consortium are strongly engaged in contributing to the IPCC and Earth Commission assessment reports: Anders Levermann for instances has been lead author of the sea-level change chapter of the 5th IPCC Assessment Report, and Ricarda Winkelmann is a member of the newly established Earth Commission, leading the Working Group 'Climate and the Cryosphere'. The Earth Commission (<https://earthcommission.org/>) was formed by the *Global Commons Alliance with the aim of providing a high-level synthesis of scientific knowledge on the biophysical processes that regulate Earth's stability and targets to ensure this stability. The commission will also explore social transformations required for sustainable development to reach these targets. Tipping points will play an important role in this regard, and the TiPACCs results will form an important knowledge source for the synthesis report.*

Our results will enter the IPCC and Earth Commission discourse through these channels, and generally via publications in ISI journals.

Task D.4: Stakeholder event to engage in expert dialogue with decision makers (M45)

Task lead: AWI, PIK

Target audience: Local government in the area of Bremen, German media and national decision makers

All partner institutes of the TiPACCs consortium have direct links to **regional (city/commune), national (government) and/or European decision makers**, and we will exploit these channels to provide relevant information. As part of the Helmholtz Climate Initiative „Regional Climate Change (REKLIM)“, Klaus Grosfeld (AWI) is engaged in the development of the “Climate Adaptation Strategy of the City-State Bremen”. Based on joint interests together with the Senator for Environment, Construction and Traffic Bremen for introducing scientific knowledge into decision making processes, a regional conference on “Climate Change in Coastal Regions” with stakeholders ranging from local authorities, NGO's, organisations maintaining the dyke, and politicians has been organized in 2015. REKLIM also was invited to

contribute to the formulation and development of the climate adaptation strategy, which has been published in 2018. We will draw from these experiences and established contacts for one **stakeholder event in Bremen/Bremerhaven (D4.11)** to be organized within TiPACCs.

There are a number of other well-established links to decision makers, also on the national and European level: Adrian Jenkins at BAS routinely contributes to written *assessments of global sea-level impacts provided to UK MPs* and works with the UK Met Office on the development of their ocean and climate models, and Hilmar Gudmundsson (UNN) provides inputs to *international structured expert judgment elicitations*. Anders Levermann and Ricarda Winkelmann at PIK frequently give presentations on sea-level change to the German Parliament and at the *United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change* (e.g., COP21 in Paris and COP23 in Bonn). Anders Levermann has also been strongly engaged in expert dialogue in his role as lead author of the sea-level change chapter of the 5th IPCC Assessment Report, and now is lead author of the Ocean, Cryosphere and Sea Level chapter of the current **6th IPCC Assessment Report**.

Task D.5: Report for policy makers – The safe operating space for Antarctica (M1-48)

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: Policy makers and the EU Commission, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs)

In view of the ambitious Paris Climate Agreement as well as the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals, policy makers are facing major challenges in the coming years concerning profound impacts on global climate and human societies for this century and beyond.

Tipping points in Antarctic climate components and their impact on future sea-level rise have become a major concern in this regard and continue to spark discourse around the globe. In order to provide policy makers with the best scientific basis on this key issue, we plan to write a **synthesis report** on our findings from the TiPACCs project **(D4.12)**. The report will combine numerical modelling results from WP1 to WP3 and provide a multi-model assessment of the processes and conditions leading to shifts from ‘cold’ to ‘warm’ oceanic conditions as well as from ‘stable’ to ‘unstable’ grounding-line configurations.

Having established the precursors leading to the Antarctic tipping points we will apply this knowledge, in combination with the long observational records from WP1 (Task 1.6), to provide a list of potential **early warning indicators**. Paleo-reconstructions and numerical modelling of the climate, Southern Ocean, and Antarctic Ice Sheet during the Last Interglacial will furthermore provide an analogue of a climate state when the tipping points were passed.

Based on TiPACCs’ theoretical, numerical and observational work, we will define a **‘safe operating space’** necessary to avoid the Antarctic tipping points being passed.

TiPACCs Deliverable D5.7

Both, the list of early warning indicators and the report on the safe operating space will be written for international scientific assessments (such as IPCC) and for policy/decision makers.

(VI) Exploitation Activities

Overview of activities

Activity	Task in DoA	Target audience
E.1 EU Polar Cluster	Task 5.5	EU Polar Cluster, Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects
E.2 Coordination with relevant EU projects and other initiatives	Task 5.5	Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects
E.3 Model intercomparison projects	Task 4.2	Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects
E.4 Management of data and model output	Task 4.3	Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

Exploitation tasks

Task E.1: EU Polar Cluster

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: EU Polar Cluster, Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

Within the TiPACCs activities, we plan to closely collaborate with the EU Polar Cluster, the polar-focused network of Horizon 2020 and Framework Programme 7 funded projects including APPLICATE, ARCSAR, ARICE, BLUE-ACTION, EU-PolarNet, ICE-ARC, iCUPE, INTAROS, INTERACT, KEPLER and NUNATARYUK.

Several of these projects focus on enhancing observations in polar regions and improving sea-level projections, and we foresee many synergies with the TiPACCs agenda. In particular, we could provide our findings on tipping points in the Southern Ocean, causing a switch from cold to warm ocean cavities, as well as insights into the critical thresholds beyond which self-enforcing mechanism such as the Marine Ice Sheet Instability drive dynamic ice loss. At the same time, we will greatly benefit from new observations and process understanding with respect to ocean and ice interactions.

Jointly, we could help provide policy-relevant information to the EU as well as the IPCC. We therefore plan to participate in EU Polar Cluster activities where possible, and present our results at workshops and conferences with EU Polar Cluster involvement.

Task E.2: Coordination with relevant EU projects and other initiatives (M1-M48)

Task lead: NORCE

Target audience: Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

Besides the EU Polar Cluster projects, we also aim at establishing operational functioning links with other existing consortia, communities, projects and organizations coordinating activities of relevance to TiPACCs. We will invite relevant (EU) project participants to our annual meetings. Additionally, we will pro-actively approach and discuss our project with other EU project members during international scientific conferences and meetings and aim for joint participation in EC requested meetings. If possible, we will aim to align our outreach activities as well. All exchange of information between TiPACCs and these other relevant projects will be synthesized through three additional deliverables (**D5.10-5.12**), one at the end of each reporting period.

Currently we have established links to the EU H2020 projects SO-CHIC and COMFORT (both initiated in 2019), and PROTECT (presently in Grant Agreement Preparation phase).

Task E.3: Model Intercomparison projects (M1-48)

Task lead: PIK

Target audience: Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

Within the scientific community we will engage in several **model intercomparison projects** (MIP) to assess the inter- and intra-model uncertainties and to foster the exchange between research groups. Some of these MIP activities are led by consortium members who are also involved in the design of the new experiments, and will therefore provide added value to the community as well as the TiPACCs project:

- **MISOMIP2**, Marine Ice Sheet-Ocean Model Intercomparison Project 2 (led by personell from UGA, UNN and PIK)
- **ISMIP6** Ice Sheet Model Intercomparison Project for CMIP6 including InitMIP-Antarctica experiments for the initialization of Antarctic ice-flow models (with contributions by Winkelmann, Jourdain)
- **ABUMIP**, Antarctic BUttrressing Model Intercomparison Project (with contributions by Gillet-Chaulet, Jourdain, Winkelmann)
- **LAR-MIP**: Linear Antarctic Response Model Intercomparison Project (led by Levermann and Winkelmann)

To ensure transparency and coordinated model development, our model codes will be made available to the general community. All models used in TiPACCs are community models and freely downloadable, e.g. from GitHub repositories (in some cases an initial user registration is required).

Task E.4: Management of data and model output (M1-M48)

Task lead: UGA

Target audience: Specialist scientific community, European and International initiatives and projects

A large amount of ocean and ice simulations will be generated in TiPACCS and will require an elaborated data management plan (**D4.2**). These data consist of ice and ocean simulations, under the form of raw model data, post-processed data for the scientific community, and end-products such as animations for a broader public. At the project kick-off meeting, a **data-management panel** was formed with one person from each modelling group. The panel is led by Nicholas Jourdain (UGA) with contributions from Jørund R. Strømsøe (NORCE), Ralph Timmermann (AWI), Adrian Jenkins (UNN) and Ronja Reese (PIK). The panel leader has made a Data Management Plan (DMP) indicating the anticipated characteristics of model outputs (e.g. file size, format) and specifying which part of the data will need to be shared within the TiPACCS consortium, and which part will be shared with the scientific community or a broader public.

The groups will organize their own computing time on national or European super computers. The full model outputs will first be stored and saved on the data servers associated with these super computers. The observational data and model outputs required for collaborations within TiPACCS will be shared through the Open Science Network (OSF, <http://osf.io>), a free web facility that proposes large storage and an interface to easily share and discuss the data within a group while controlling files access. OSF will also be used to archive the most important outputs and share them publicly beyond this project. It also provides the functionality to attribute a DOI to each uploaded dataset. This strategy was successfully used by several TiPACCS participants in the MISOMIP project. Some final products dedicated to the international scientific community will be submitted to centres open for archiving, publishing, and re-use of data, such as World Data Center PANGAEA (<https://www.pangaea.de>) and QUANTARCTICA (<http://quantarctica.npolar.no>). The dissemination of data (e.g. animations) to a broader public will be undertaken through our dissemination plan (Task 4.5).

Our group will also aim to provide reproducible results and we will therefore make our model configurations publicly available. We will deposit our configuration files (e.g. revision ID, compilation keys, namelists, etc) on preserved repositories associated with DOIs. For this we will use Zenodo (<http://zenodo.org>) which is a free platform that can be connected to other applications such as <https://github.com>. Zenodo is integrated into reporting lines for research funded by the European Commission via OpenAIRE. Example of Zenodo preserved repositories for NEMO configurations used in publications can be found on <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1067647>.

(VII) Expected Impacts

Furthering our understanding and quantifying the likelihood of tipping points in the Southern Ocean and Antarctic Ice Sheet is a highly timely and relevant topic with regards to sea-level projections, with strong implications for coastal populations, ecosystems and infrastructures worldwide. TiPACCs results are therefore likely to be picked up in the general public discourse, by the media as well as stakeholders and policy makers.

In the following, we assess expected impacts of the research programme and guidance (e.g. assessment of the 'safe operating space') to local, national, and international decision makers.

Expected impacts of the research programme

Support major international scientific assessments such as the IPCC.

Several of the researchers involved in TiPACCs advice policy makers on the global impact of changes in the mass balance of the Antarctic Ice Sheet, by meeting with stakeholders ranging from local authorities, NGO's, governmental agencies maintaining the dyke, and politicians organized together with, e.g., the Senator for Environment, Construction and Traffic Bremen or the Research Council of Norway. Others contribute to written assessments of global sea-level impacts provided to UK MPs, cooperate with the World Wildlife Fund (WWF) in adult education or frequently give presentations on sea-level change to the German Parliament and at the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (e.g., COP21 in Paris and COP23 in Bonn).

Moreover, members of TiPACCs will contribute to the 6th Assessment Report (AR6), being published in the first half of 2022, in time for the first UNFCCC global stocktake under the Paris Agreement in 2023. Specifically, Gael Durand (UGA) contributed to the IPCC AR6 through participation in the Scoping Meeting in 2017 as a national expert.

As stated in AR5 related to the global mean sea-level (GMSL) rise, there is high confidence in projections of warming of the ocean (thermal expansion), but only medium confidence in projections of ocean-driven glacier/ice sheet mass loss, especially, the contributions from rapid dynamical changes of the ice sheet, estimated from a combination of process-based modelling, statistical extrapolation of recent trends, and informed judgement. Thus, our contribution to AR6 will at first focus on increasing the confidence in future sea-level projections, in particular with respect to the possibility of abrupt and large-scale changes in the state of the Antarctic marginal seas and the ice sheet. Secondly, and perhaps even more important, TiPACCs will clarify the potential collapse of marine-based sectors of the West Antarctic Ice Sheet that could cause GMSL to rise substantially above the likely range during the 21st century.

The consortium members have direct links to major scientific organisations. Hilmar Gudmundsson, UNN, is the vice-president of the International Glaciological Society and a past president of the EGU Division on Cryospheric Sciences. TiPACCs researchers organize the FRISP (Forum for Research into Ice Shelf Processes) - A. Jenkins is the chair and H. Hellmer and S. Østerhus are national representatives. FRISP acts as an Expert Group in SCAR (Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research). Therefore, international workshops and reports to SCAR will benefit greatly from the project collaboration and deliverables.

Increase confidence in climate change projections.

Climate change projections feed into local and global policy decisions, and thus, the projections as a tangible result constitute a major focus of research. To achieve confidence in climate projections, the underlying models should prove to be adequate, i.e., how well the model results (a) fit with observation-based data (empirical accuracy) and (b) agree with other models or model versions (robustness). For long-term projections, a climate model must represent sufficiently all physical, chemical and biological processes of the climate system that are relevant for the temporal and spatial evolution of the climate variables of interest. Related to sea-level rise, a bundle of key processes is used, including observations, models and theoretical approaches on ice-sheet mass balance and ice sheet dynamics. Within this framework, TiPACCs is designed to assess the proximity, rate, and reversibility of climate change induced tipping points in the marginal seas and ice sheet of Antarctica within the 21st century. Our approach, combining paleo-modelling and paleo-reconstructions with a focus on the Southern Ocean and Antarctic Ice Sheet during a previous warm period, will provide a better understanding of the dynamics and interaction of both tipping points and their specific impact on global sea level, i.e., due to a partly disintegrated Antarctic Ice Sheet. Thus, TiPACCs will contribute to improve confidence in future climate/sea level predictions.

As we are addressing the question of tipping points, not the question of estimating future mass loss, we do not need to involve a full coupling of the atmosphere-ocean-ice sheet system. Of course, by investigating and addressing the possibility of tipping points being crossed, we do provide valuable information for any estimates of future ice loss. But it's important to understand the difference between 1) assessing the possibility of tipping points within the Southern Ocean and the Antarctic Ice Sheet, and 2) future mass loss estimates from the Antarctic Ice Sheet given particular emission scenarios. We are here addressing the former and not the latter.

Provide added-value to decision and policy makers.

The impact of human-influenced climate change is increasingly recognized globally. Therefore, the need for climate research and information "ready to use" in decision-making contexts for climate change adaptation and mitigation is growing. Starting with

the 2015 Paris Agreement, governments have launched a process to coordinate national policies and to “manage” the climate impact by adaptation and mitigation measures (i.e., to minimize global warming). Today, policy makers require more data and analysis but also argue about credibility, plausibility, and robustness of the underlying information. Thus, the most important added value of TiPACCs is the decrease of uncertainty, inevitable in climate change projections due to the system’s natural variability, unknown interactions of its components, and/or unforeseeable emission rates. TiPACCs will illustrate the sensitivity of Antarctic climate components to environmental change as well as their interaction and possible feedback mechanisms.

First, we will reduce model uncertainties by simulating and inter-comparing a range of earth system processes, which are relevant to the Antarctic Ice Sheet mass balance. For example, by combining model results - using a multi-model approach - with multi-decadal ocean observations, we will provide a **list of early warning indicators** (D1.9) for the approach of a tipping point (Objective 4) in the Southern Ocean and will **identify the possible safe operating space** (D4.12). TiPACCs numerical models and outputs will deliver not only diagnostics but will also **reduce the uncertainty in future projections** as they will point to critical interactions and feedbacks at (a) the Antarctic continental shelf break, regulating the onshore flow of warm waters, and (b) the grounding lines of Antarctic ice shelves, controlling the discharge of inland ice. Our deliverables (see Section 3.1 and WP1-4) will provide timely and useful information to decision-makers including answers to decision-makers’ specific questions like: Are the processes causing a tipping of the ocean state reversible and/or manageable?

Second, the challenge for decision-makers arises from the fact that climate change is only one of many factors that influence human health, ecosystems, and social well-being, TiPACCs findings will thus be considered in relation with other important stresses. Third, an additional challenge all policy makers are facing is how to use management recommendations provided by climate change assessments to develop new policies or amend running programs. Thus, our dissemination strategy is targeted **not only to produce more information on the topic but to support decision-making** (WP4, Task 4.7-4.8). Europe’s leadership in climate policy is relying on such information and efforts. The EU, due to its very nature, is ideally positioned to contribute to climate negotiations and to shape the international climate agenda. This in turn, will lead to a higher recognition of climate science “made in Europe”.

Sustain Europe's leadership in climate science.

Europe has built up and is hosting world-class national climate research facilities and is implementing the collaborative realisation of ambitious research goals by its pan-EU and national programmes. The TiPACCs consortium is built from leading research groups in ocean circulation and ice-flow modelling in Europe (see also section 3.3, consortium as a whole and section 4, GA). According to science metrics, the researchers in TiPACCs publish in the most prestigious journals in their field (Table

2.1, GA). TiPACCs will also make a substantial contribution to the European Research Area (ERA) and the Antarctic research community due to the central role its members hold in the FRISP community.

In addition to the high impact science output expected during the last part of the project and following years, the PDRAs trained in the project will be an important legacy of the project in decades to come. To encourage researcher mobility and providing a training environment for the PDRAs in the project and other scientists in ice shelf related climate research by organizing one workshop for the PDRAs, facilitate research stays within the consortium and allocating time specifically for this at the annual meetings. The coordinator will actively pursue to assist the PDRAs in applying for Marie Skłodowska-Curie actions by utilizing the extensive scientific network of the consortium.

Finally, TiPACCs will put effort into exploiting synergies in **collaboration with other consortia funded through this call** as well as with those active in the field across the globe. The consortium has agreed to the following key performance goals:

- To accelerate the development of tipping points related research by combining capacities of research institutions and maximising our complementarities and synergies, and collaboration with international partners from our network: This will be achieved by creation/preparation of **new collaborative projects** that is going to be initiated by each participant of the consortium during TiPACCs to exploit new knowledge and research results in the field. In total the PIs in TiPACCs are expected to continue **developing national and international projects in synergy with TiPACCs** that will initiated by each participant of the consortium.
- To develop training, education and outreach material according to our dissemination plan and to invite with the other consortia funded under this call, in particular from topic **“Improving the understanding of key climate processes for reducing uncertainty in climate projections and predictions”** and **“Ice-core drilling in East Antarctica”** and **organise one workshop together with these projects**

Substantial impact not mentioned in the work programme

As the global as well as local sea level rise poses risks to human health, ecosystems, social and cultural systems, and economic development - but also provides opportunities - it is of highest relevance to know more and better about indicators, implications, feedbacks, and projections of the anthropogenic interference with the climate system. According to the latest analysis performed by the IMBIE team (2018), from 1992 to 2017 the Antarctic Ice Sheet lost almost 3 trillion tons of ice, causing a sea-level rise of 8mm. The strongest trend between 1992 and the last five years of the survey was observed for the West Antarctic Ice Sheet, which drains into relatively warm continental shelf seas. Here, the mass loss per year more than tripled, now being

equivalent to a sea-level rise of 0.44 mm/yr. By 2100, **70% of the global coastlines** will experience the effects of rising sea-levels. In the absence of effective mitigation, frequency and amplitude of sea-level extremes and coastal inundation as well as GMSL rise will accelerate over the coming centuries and will continue for millennia (Clark et al., 2018; Nature Climate Change). The economic burden out of these effects have been modelled and is of high interest, e.g., for reinsurance companies, state finance, private investment agents, and the general public. TiPACCs will contribute to the improvement of these models by providing insight into the temporal evolution of tipping points and possible feedback mechanisms which either increase or mitigate the Antarctic ice sheet mass loss. Thus, a better-informed society and better-informed professionals will be capable of making informed decisions towards climate change adaptation and mitigation.

For example, the **infrastructure, transport sector, and port industries** and communities are addressed: 90% of the world's freight moves by ship and seaports play a crucial role in the global economy as transportation hubs for the vast majority of goods transported around the world, growing rapidly. To remain efficient and resilient, seaports need to anticipate the impacts of climate change and proactively prepare for sea level rise, increased flooding, and more frequent extreme storm events by investing heavily into new infrastructure. This is not reflected in today's infrastructure related decision making across the industry and the communities operating the seaports. Anders Levermann at PIK is the scientific coordinator of the Zeean project (www.zeean.net), a project where the original underlying idea is to develop a model that is capable of modeling the impacts of climate change on the global supply chain network. By identifying safe operating spaces, TiPACCs has the potential to contribute valuable information to infrastructure planners.

Moreover, once being regarded as an obvious risk, knowledge on climate change has started to drive the **markets for climate risk decisions and management**. NORCE is a partner in the Norwegian Centre for Climate Services with main responsibility to feed climate system knowledge into its products and is currently developing a centre for climate risk together with leading Norwegian industry partners.

Barriers and obstacles that may determine whether impacts will be achieved

While climate change research is very comprehensive and integrates nearly all scientific disciplines, polar issues have been gaining importance at the political agenda across Europe only during the past 20 years. The rising level of research funding and investments made by the EU and the national governments clearly demonstrate how critical polar research outcomes are for informing policy. However, Antarctica is too remote and difficult to access to survey the ice sheet and its fringing marginal seas completely. Trends in the ocean and the ice cover may be only assessed by improved instrumentation, autonomously operating vehicles, satellite data, and numerical models considering all components of the climate system. This is especially true due

to additional **specific challenges of polar research** that demand for **extensive and strong cooperation at all levels**, i.e., the need for the implementation of international networks that foster the exchange of research results; the maintenance of expensive research vessels and stations; complex logistics; the need for relevant funding priorities. Regarding the **international political developments**, e.g., Brexit and the US-drop out of climate change research, impose a severe risk of losing reliable partners and funding opportunities for polar research during the next decade. Additionally, there is a critical need for advanced **model data integration and data processing capacities** as well as for additional investment to expand the early warning indicators towards the poles and integrate them in a global warning system. This is still a shortcoming at all participating institutes in TiPACCs, which is expected to be minimized by acquisition of additional national funding of the project. Moreover, the speed of changes in the ocean and cryosphere sometimes overrun the long research cycles with respect to necessary skill development, cumbersome data collection, data analysis, and publishing. Such a **timeline for research projects and careers** sometimes means that scientific approaches and their realization have to be updated, especially in a rapidly changing environment such as the poles. TiPACCs participants are aware of attracting young people and the public by, e.g., presenting the project towards primary and secondary school children, layman reports in newspapers, and TV productions (see communication plan, 2.2).

Measures to maximise impact

TiPACCs will pay particular attention to achieving a wide impact of the project's scientific work on ocean and ice sheet tipping points and its contribution to knowledge on the Southern Ocean and Antarctic Ice Sheet in general. The communication, dissemination and exploitation activities detailed above will proceed throughout the duration of the project, and exploitation will continue beyond.

A number of activities aim at ensuring wide visibility and recognition of the project as part of the CDE campaign. These actions include:

- Participation in relevant conferences, workshops, international meetings (such as EGU, AGU, IGS, FRISP, SCAR and WAIS)
- Targeted engagement of stakeholders through e.g. stakeholder workshop in Bremen/Bremerhaven, open day events, working group discussions.
- Establishing synergies with other projects and initiatives (e.g. other projects to be funded under the same call with a focus on improved understanding of the climate system, and related tipping points, and projects listed in the DoA, such as FISS, EAIS, PROPHET, and DOMINOES ES and the different MIPs to extend the scope of dissemination to new areas and national and international networks.
- Open access publications to reach out to other research groups.

- Lectures and information to school kids, students, PhDs.

TiPACCs will in particular address those **groups or initiatives**, where decision makers, policy advisers, academic or industry partners, or all, have joined forces to stimulate cooperation, dissemination and exploitation in specific areas of interest related to climate changes and the role of Antarctic ice shelves in relation to that. These groups will include, among others:

- Relevant national and European associations/federations, where TiPACCs partners are members, e.g. European Geosciences Union (EGU), International Glaciological Society (IGS), West Antarctic Ice Sheet Initiative (WAIS), Forum for Research into Ice Shelf Processes (FRISP).
- Scientific Committee on Antarctic Research (SCAR), World Climate Research Programme (WCRP), International Arctic Science Committee (IASC), Southern Ocean Observing System (SOOS) and European Climate Research Alliance (ECRA).
- European Polar Board (EPB), an independent organisation that focuses on major European strategic priorities in both the Arctic and the Antarctic regions. Current EPB membership includes research institutes, funding agencies, scientific academies and polar operators from across Europe.
- TV production companies, authors, editors, climate publishers network (CPN) and also tour operators of Antarctic cruises, e.g. "Hurtigruten" (www.hurtigruten.no).
- Early warning and response research, information and planning networks, i.e. World Meteorological Organization's Global Cryosphere Watch (GCW).

The exploitation activities are closely related to dissemination, and the consortium partners strive for both **direct and indirect exploitation** of the results. As for academic/research organisations, our main strategic goals are primarily not linked directly to new products but to advance research and academic progress and careers. Thus, we are interested in using newly gained knowledge as input to accelerate research, high-impact scientific publications and advanced teaching purposes. Moreover, we will also use the results to develop partnerships with existing or new contact networks. Additionally, raising the profile of our researchers through publication and promotion of the project results will lead to a stronger capacity for attracting further research funding. The project integrates advances in fundamental knowledge into applied oriented research, with the objective to develop the project ideas from **theoretical assumptions towards tangible results for further use in decision-making processes**.

Further exploitation of project results by industry will be encouraged through contribution to workshops facilitated by our established industry contacts (e.g.

Aanderaa, Norway and DeVeLogic, Germany). Finally, TiPACCs will establish the foundations for the next step on the way towards commercial success of companies in the field of risk assessment, risk management, and policy advice.

Moreover, there is the possibility to develop an early warning system out of the results, and to integrate the project results into the tipping point interrelation framework, see also Section 1.3.1.

In general, the elements of an early warning system are: knowledge about risks, a warning service, communication channels, and of course, response infrastructure and capabilities. The early warning indicators would flow into the knowledge element and would specifically refer to knowledge of how the Southern Ocean and Antarctic Ice Sheet respond to climate change.

Summary: How the proposed measures will help to achieve the expected impact of the project

To summarize, TiPACCs communication, dissemination and exploitation activities will help to achieve the expected impacts as follows:

- Supporting major international scientific assessments such as the IPCC by dissemination of project results into AR6, chapter 13 on sea level projections by PIK and by publishing in major journals to receive recognition in the scientific community in the field;
- Increasing confidence in climate change projections by closing knowledge gaps and combining observational elements with modelling and earth system interactions, and by efforts to increase credibility, robustness, and applicability of project results in projections on sea level rise;
- Providing added-value to decision and policy makers by discussion and stakeholder workshop on interpretation and usability of results in their decision-making process and to deliver early warning indicators that may be further used for warning systems and development of response strategies
- Sustaining Europe's leadership in climate science by exploiting European research capabilities and existing knowledge/running projects, and to maximise effect of funding by creating synergies from the high-level research infrastructures in this complex, expensive, and broad but highly relevant and research field. Teaching younger scientists and thus attracting future competences in the research field.
- Building awareness of the TiPACCs results using a variety of communication and aggregation tools, widely disseminating the project objectives and research results to the scientific community, end-users and the general public.

Stakeholders, decision makers	Public	Research Community	Target groups
<p>Politicians and decision makers: dialogue with and reports to parliament members, national ministries and agencies</p> <p>IPCC AR: chapter on Oceans, Cryosphere and Sea level rise</p> <p>Workshops: Working group meetings at EGU, IGS, SOOS, WAIS, SCAR, FRISP and WCRP</p>	<p>Open days: BAS at Cambridge Science Festival, scientists' talks at primary/secondary schools, AWI open ship day and science on the road, Girls days, researcher grand prix, research nights, science slams, sci.-meet-arts, open doors, guided tours at all participating institutes</p> <p>Videos: Four videos (5-15 min) will be produced and published on established YouTube channels, and other relevant websites</p> <p>Layman publication: Forskning.no, newspaper, IAATO leaflets, children book</p>	<p>Synergies with other (EU)-Projects: FP7 ICE2SEA, FP7 NAACLIM, ERC Syn Grant Ice2ice, WAPITI, MSCA OceanIS, ERC COMPASS, ERC WACSWAIN, MSCA MIMOP</p> <p>Scientific publications with green and gold open access: The Cryosphere, Journal of Glaciology, Journal of Physical Oceanography, Geophysical Research Letters, Journal of Geophysical Research, Nature (and 'by-products'), Science, JGR-Oceans, J. Climate, Ocean Science, Geoscientific Model Development</p> <p>Lectures: research results and methodology will be prepared for lectures at universities and summer schools, e.g. Karthaus summer school on Ice Sheets and Glaciers in the Climate System, Elmer/Ice annual courses&workshop, Climate-MOOC (UiB), Ua annual courses&workshop (UNN).</p> <p>Conferences: EGU, WAIS, AGU, IGS annual meetings, FRISP, SCAR, IACS, and SOOS events</p>	<p>Specific activities towards target groups</p>
<p>Website: Hosted by UniRes and kept updated throughout project duration</p> <p>Social Media: participants currently combine ~200.000 followers on their institution's twitter (75.000) and Facebook (125.000) accounts today. These will be used for spreading news from the project. Researchers in the consortium regularly post on science blogs</p> <p>Digital and printed material/Video: production of flyer and of 3 videos about project and main findings, development of interactive web-based maps to demonstrate the existence of tipping points in the Ice Sheet and Southern Ocean, based on the model runs and basic info</p> <p>Newsletters: All participants have a very active PR department, publishing regular newsletters, news on the website and press releases which frequently get covered by media outlets worldwide. TIPACCs will feed the PR departments with highlights from the project.</p>			<p>Main activities towards all target groups</p>
<p>Information and guidance how to use this information in policy, risk management, infrastructure investment, logistics, port operators, communities.</p>			<p>Societal and industrial impact</p>

Figure 3: Summary of communication, dissemination and exploitation activities (Figure 9 of the Grant Agreement).

(IX) Follow-up of Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation activities

Throughout this plan we have presented and elaborated on multiple CDE activities in order to reach out to a wide range of audiences. Ensuring achievement of the expected impacts we have to be active on many different platforms both digital and face-to-face. Below is an overview table that we will use to follow-up and document all specific activities, filling them under the in this document described Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Activities. The related Tasks and Deliverables as defined in the DoA are also indicated. The CDE plan is a “living” document maintained and updated by the CDE manager that will monitor and coordinate the activities in the consortium. For internal purposes the overview will act as a record of CDE activities. At the internal website the CDE plan will be made available to the consortium.

Activity	Task / Deliverable	Specific activities	Date
C.1 Project website	Task 4.1 / D4.1	TiPACCs website (www.tipaccs.eu) established and regularly be updated.	From Oct 2019
C.2 Newsletters and press releases	Task 4.1	Press release before the Kick-off meeting.	2 nd Oct 2019
		Newsletter Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research „TiPACCs kick-off meeting“	11 th Oct 2019
		University Press, UNN: „£4m study to investigate if climate change will drive the Antarctic Ice Sheet towards a tipping point“	21 st Oct 2019
		North scientists researching the dangers of melting Antarctic ice sheets.	21 st Oct 2019
		Press release on the projections of ice sheet contributions to sea-level rise in Futura-Sciences, Les Échos, L'Express and Ça M'intéresse.	17 th September 2020
		Stability Check on Antarctica Reveals High Risk for Long-Term Sea-Level Rise. Press release at Potsdam Institute for Climate Impact Research (PIK).	23 rd September 2020
C.3 Social media strategy @TiPACCs_EU	Task 4.1	Twitter account @TiPACCs:EU established. Regular tweets	From Oct 2020
		Social media: EU-PolarNet Facebook post with the animated video	27 nd Jan 2020

		Eisschilde, Kippprozesse und Meeresspiegelanstieg. Twitter post.	23rd November 2020
C.4 Interactive maps	Task 4.6/ D4.10		
C.5 Video series	Task 4.5/ D4.6-D4.9	First video online on YouTube: TiPACCs – Antarctica and tipping points	5 th Feb 2020
C.6 Communications training for TiPACCs members	Task 4.4/ D4.3-D4.4		
C.7 High-school teacher training	Task 4.4 / D4.5		
C.8 Further communication activities	Task 4.1	Norwegian Broadcaster NRK news program “Studerer issmelting i Antarktis“	2 nd Oct 2019
		NRK web «Norske forskere skal finne sydpol-smeltingens "point of no return"»	3 rd Oct 2019
		University Press: „Leder forskning på isen på Sydpolen med Europas fremste“	3 rd Oct 2019
		University Press: «Svein ville pensjonere seg: — Men dette kunne jeg ikke gå glipp av»	3 rd Oct 2019
		Norwegian broadcaster TV: «Slik vil norske Svein løse klimagåten i havet»	3 rd Oct 2019
		Univ. Bergen Museum: Yearbook «Draumen om straumen»	15 th Oct 2019
		„Sea level and ice sheets“ Meeting with Norwegian parliament member	22 nd Nov 2019
		Workshop for theater production about climate change	26 nd Nov 2019
		Bergen Rotary Club: «Havstraumar og klima»	27 th Nov 2019
		UGA: Presentation to students from high school	18 th Dec 2019
		Online climate news: “Greenland’s Nearing a Climate Tipping Point. How Long Warming Lasts Will Decide Its Fate, Study Says”	23 rd Dec 2019
		Reklim website (www.reklim.de) Presentation of TiPACCs	9 th April 2020
		Norwegian Broadcaster NRK web: «Svein skal finne ut om verden drukner»	11 th April 2020

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		Hysteresis for Dummies – Why history matters. Blogpost, EGU website	12 th April 2020
		Eis, Kipppunkte und Meeresspiegelanstieg. Public lecture. PIK and the Museum für Naturkunde	17 th July 2020
		Interview in regional TV JT 19/20 France 3 Alpes showing the first TiPACCs video.	22 nd September 2020
		Shocking computer animation shows how Antarctica could emerge from the ice if global warming continues unabated causing the frozen continent to melt and sea levels to rise. Daily mail, online news.	23 rd September 2020
		Antarctica smelt sprongsgewijs. NRC Handelsblad. Dutch newspaper.	23 rd September 2020
		Global warming may lead to practically irreversible Antarctic melting. Science news.	23 rd September 2020
		Stability check on Antarctica reveals high risk for long-term sea-level rise. Phys.org, British news aggregator.	23 rd September 2020
		Melting Antarctic ice will raise sea level by 2.5 metres – even if Paris climate goals are met, study finds. Website article in The Guardian, UK.	23 rd September 2020
		Interview in the regional TV JT 19/20 France 3 Alpes showing the first TiPACCs video. Website article	24 th September 2020
		"Was wir jetzt verlieren, ist für immer verloren" Website article in Der Spiegel, Germany.	24 th September 2020
		Antarktis-Eisschmelze hat weltweit dramatische Folgen. T-Online.de, German news portal.	24 th September 2020
		Erwärmung macht Eisverlust in der Antarktis unumkehrbar. Article in Austrian newspaper.	27 th September 2020
		Espectacular simulación de como la Antártida podría perder su capa de hielo en un futuro. La Vanguardia, Spanish news website.	29 th September 2020

		Remote control of Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf melt rates by the Antarctic Slope Current. Talk Univ. of Cambridge.	21 st October 2020
		Remote control of Filchner-Ronne Ice Shelf melt rates by the Antarctic Slope Current. Talk, Australian National Univ.	22 nd October 2020
		Presentation «Ice sheet - climate interactions» at the ESA Polar Science Workshop.	28 th October 2020
		How small changes can make a big difference: tipping points in Antarctica. Blog post at EGU website.	13 th November 2020
		Are we melting Antarctica irreversibly? Podcast at the Bjerknes Centre for Climate Research.	15 th November 2020
		Presentation «Is og vippepunkt» at the Bjerknes Center for Climate Research anniversary seminar (in Norwegian).	30 th Nov 2020
		Eisschilde, Kippprozesse und Meeresspiegelanstieg. Online presentation at the Nachhaltigkeitswoche des Nordens.	23 rd November 2020
D.1 Publications and special issue	Task 4.2/ D.1.4, D.1.7, D1.8, D1.9, D2.2., D2.5, D3.2	Geophysical Research Letters (46/23): Instantaneous Antarctic ice sheet mass loss driven by thinning ice shelves.	20 th Nov 2019
D.2 Scientific conferences and workshops	Task 4.2	Early Warning for the Marine Ice Sheet Instability. Presentation at PIK.	17 th March 2020
		Early Warning for the Marine Ice Sheet Instability. Seminar	8 th April 2020
		TiPACCs – Tipping points in Antarctic Climate Components. EGU scientific conference	5 th May 2020
		Antarctic ice dynamics - from deep past to deep future. EGU scientific conference	5 th May
		The tipping points of Pine Island Glacier, West Antarctica. EGU scientific conference	6 th may 2020
		The role of history and strength of the oceanic forcing in sea-level	7 th May 2020

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		projections from Antarctica with the Parallel Ice Sheet Model. EGU scientific conference.	
		Modelling Ice Sheets on Greenland and Antarctica. Geustlecture at Univ. Potsdam	29 th May 2020
		Modelling Ice Sheets on Greenland and Antarctica. Geustlecture at Univ. Potsdam	2 nd June
		FRISP 2020 Virtual Conference. PIK were organization of the conference.	16 th June 2020
		Ice-ocean interactions in Antarctica - What drives future sea-level rise? Presentation, Univ. of Heidelberg.	23 rd July 2020
		Coupled ice-ocean simulations of the Amundsen Sea glaciers. Presentation at scientific conference	10 th August 2020
		The Hysteresis of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. Talk.	2 nd September 2020
		The role of history and strength of the oceanic forcing in sea-level projections from Antarctica with the Parallel Ice Sheet Model. Presentation at the WAIS workshop.	22 nd September 2020
		Presenting the project at a seminar gathering Antarctic researchers in Norway.	7 th October 2020
		Calotte Antarctique, augmentations du niveau des mers et modélisation. Polar week, France.	10 th November 2020
		Online Elmer/Ice beginner course. Organisation of a Workshop.	14-27 th November 2020
		Last Interglacial Southern Ocean - Antarctic climate. Poster presentation & discussion at AGU fall meeting, online conference.	7 th December 2020
		The Hysteresis of the Antarctic Ice Sheet. AGU fall meeting, online conference.	16 th December 2020
D.3 IPCC and Earth Commission	Task 4.7	Earth Commission Meeting	19 th November 2019
D.4 Stakeholder event	Task 4.7/ D4.11	TiPACCs session at the Science to policy event	17 th Nov 2020

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D.5 Report for policy makers	Task 4.8/ D4.12		
E.1 EU Polar Cluster	Task 5.5	Presenting the project	27th November 2020
	Task 5.5	Participation in first online meeting.	27th November 2020
E.2 Coordination with relevant EU projects and other initiatives	Task 5.5	Presentation at the kick off meeting for the PROTECT project.	30th September 2020
		Collaboration with COMFORT during the EU Climate Science2Policy event	
E.3 Model intercomparison projects	Task 4.2		
E.4 Management of data and model output	Task 4.3/ D4.2	Data Management Plan and following Zenodo User guide submitted.	30 th Jan 2020